

ANALYSIS AND OPTIMIZATION OF WEB CORE COMPOSITE SANDWICH SHELLS SUBJECTED TO AXIAL COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

Web core sandwich cylindrical shells with faces of specially orthotropic composite materials are discussed herein. When these shells are subjected to axially symmetric compressive loads, analytical methods are available to analyze and design such shells to prevent overstressing, overall buckling, core shear instability, face plate buckling, and web element buckling; these are presented herein. In addition, analytical methods to determine the configuration and materials systems to achieve absolute minimum weight are developed and also presented herein. These procedures provide the means to select the face thickness (t_f), the core depth (h_c), the web plate element stiffness (t_c), and the circumferential spacing between web plate elements (d_c) to attain minimum weight for a given face and core material. One major characteristic of web core sandwich that differs from honeycomb core and foam core sandwich constructions discussed in References 1 through 3 is that the core carries a portion of the axial load. In addition, a factor of merit is developed for selecting the best material system to attain minimum weight. In addition, the methods developed clearly define the maximum axial compressive load the shell can withstand without failing.

1. INTRODUCTION

It has been shown by many authors that through the use of sandwich construction, the flexural stiffness is several hundred times, and the maximum flexural stresses developed are a small fraction of those associated with a monocoque construction of approximately the same weight, using the same materials. Even with these advantages, it is often desirable and always interesting to develop methods by which to structurally optimize the sandwich construction to:

1. determine the absolute minimum weight obtainable for a given type of sandwich, loading, and material system,
2. rationally select the best material to minimize structural weight,
3. rationally compare the use of one type of sandwich construction with other types of sandwich,
4. rationally compare the best sandwich construction with alternative configurations (rib-reinforced, etc.),

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5. select the best stacking sequence for the laminated composite material construction,
6. suggest to material scientists and suppliers how to develop improved materials for sandwich construction,
7. to rationally compare the optimum sandwich weight to non-optimum constructions where restrictions such as cost, manufacturability, etc., suggest other solutions; i.e., a cost per unit weight penalty function can be easily generated.

2. METHODS OF ANALYSIS FOR WEB CORE SANDWICH CYLINDRICAL SHELLS SUBJECTED TO AXIALLY COMPRESSIVE LOADS

A web core construction consists of two faces connected by a long, thin set of plates running the length of the shell whose mid-surfaces are perpendicular to the mid-surface of the shell faces, as shown in Figure 1.

For the shell subjected to an axially symmetric compressive load, P , as shown in Figure 2, the axial load per unit of circumference, N_x , is given as

$$N_x = P / 2\pi R \tag{1}$$

Figure 1. Cross-section of Web-core Shell Construction

Figure 2. Circular Cylindrical Shell

Because in this construction a portion of the axial load is carried by the core as well as the faces, a balance of the axial strains, along with the fact that the sum of the face and core loads must be N_x above, the resulting relations are:

$$\sigma_{cx} = \frac{E_{cx}}{E_{fx}} \sigma_{fx} \quad (2)$$

$$N_x = \sigma_{fx} \left[\frac{E_{cx}}{E_{fx}} \frac{t_c h_c}{d_c} + 2t_f \right] \quad (3)$$

where σ_{cx} and σ_{fx} are the axial compressive stresses in the core and face, E_{cx} and E_{fx} are the axial compressive elastic modulus of the core and face materials. The upper limit on the axial load that can be carried by the shell is dictated by the maximum allowable stress of either the core or face material. In many constructions, web core sandwich utilizes the same material for core and face; in that case

$$\sigma_{cx} = \sigma_{fx} \equiv \sigma_x \quad (2a)$$

$$N_x = \sigma_x \left[\frac{t_c h_c}{d_c} + 2t_f \right] \quad (3a)$$

Equations for overall buckling of a specially orthotropic shells, developed by Reese and Bert, Reference 4, provide a simple, accurate equation for overall buckling that is amenable to easy computation while retaining accuracy.

$$(\sigma_{fx})_{cr} = \frac{\phi h_c}{R} \left[\frac{E_x E_\theta}{1 - \nu_{x\theta} \nu_{\theta x}} \right]^{1/2} \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{2} \left[\phi \left(\frac{E_x E_\theta}{1 - \nu_{x\theta} \nu_{\theta x}} \right)^{1/2} \frac{t_f}{R G_{xzc}^1} \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\phi = 1 \text{ or } \left[\frac{2G_{x\theta} \left[1 + (\nu_{x\theta} \nu_{\theta x})^{1/2} \right]}{(E_x E_\theta)^{1/2}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

whichever is smaller. In (4), G_{xzc}^1 is the effective transverse shear modulus of the core in the xz plane. In the web core construction,

$$G_{xzc}^1 = \frac{G_{xz} t_c}{d_c} \quad (6)$$

where G_{xz} is the in-plane shear modulus of the core material.

A second mode of buckling is core shear instability, given by:

$$(\sigma_{fx})_{cr} = \frac{G_{xzc}^1 h_c}{2t_f} \quad (7)$$

This is the same equation used by Reese and Bert (Reference 4) for shells, and used by Vinson for sandwich plates and shells (References 1 through 3). Since it is a local instability, it can be used for beams, plates, and shells.

Another local buckling that can occur is buckling of the face plate element between the web core supports. One established equation is given by Timoshenko and Gere (Reference 5):

$$\sigma_{ix} = \frac{\pi^2 E_{of} t_f^2}{3(1 - \nu_{x\theta} \nu_{\theta x})_f d_c^2} \quad (8)$$

where E_0 is defined by

$$2E_0 = (E_x E_\theta)^{1/2} + \nu_{\theta x} E_x + 2G_{x\theta} (1 - \nu_{x\theta} \nu_{\theta x}) \quad (9)$$

Likewise, local buckling of the core element may occur because it is carrying part of the axial load. Again, the governing equations given by Timoshenko and Gere (Reference 5):

$$\sigma_{cx} = \frac{\pi^2 E_{oc} t_c^2}{3(1 - \nu_{x\theta} \nu_{\theta x})_c h_c^2} \quad (10)$$

In the above, overall buckling, core shear instability, face plate buckling, and web-plate buckling are synonymous with failure as is overstressing of the face or core material. For design and analysis, one can select a material system and the geometric variables in order that a shell of mean radius R , length L , subjected to an axial compressive load P will not undergo overstressing, nor any of the modes of buckling, in order to prevent failure.

However, it would be valuable to have an analytical procedure that would select t_f , h_c , t_c , and d_c to insure minimum weight for the shell. It is seen that along with the four geometric variables, there are four independent buckling modes, a fortuitous situation.

3. WEIGHT EQUATION

Whether the shell is optimized or not, the weight equation is given by

$$W = 2\rho_f t_f + \rho_c^1 h_c + W_{ad} \quad (11)$$

where W is the weight per unit mid-surface area, ρ_f is the weight density of the face material, and W_{ad} is the equivalent weight per unit mid-surface area of any bonding or attaching material connecting the face and the core elements. ρ_c^1 is the equivalent weight density of the core per unit mid-surface area given by

$$\rho_c^1 = \rho_c \frac{t_c}{d_c} \quad (12)$$

where ρ_c is the actual weight density of the core plate material.

4. OPTIMIZATION TO ATTAIN MINIMUM WEIGHT

Because there are four geometric variables and four buckling equations, this suggests a unique solution may be attainable for the construction.

Since any of the instabilities causes structural failure, it follows that the most efficient structure occurs when all four buckling stresses are equal. This follows the philosophy of the weakest link in the chain theory. If the various buckling modes occur at different stresses, then some material is being used inefficiently and can be shifted or eliminated to reduce weight and/or increase the load carrying ability of the structure. This philosophy has been used to structurally optimize honeycomb core, foam core, web core, and truss core sandwich panels subjected to in-plane compressive and shear loads, and their combination. It has also been used to optimize foam core and honeycomb core sandwich cylindrical shells subjected to in-plane axial compression (References 1-3).

In this philosophy, all four buckling stresses are equated and labeled σ_o , the optimum face stress. Of course, the upper bound of σ_o is the allowable face material strength. In what follows, for brevity, it is assumed that the same material is used for face and core, and W_{ad} is taken as zero. Manipulating (2a), (3a), (4) through (10), and (12) results in the following equations for the geometric variables as a function of the optimum face stress, σ_o : In the process it is seen that in (4) the bracketed quantity is almost equal to unity, but will be labeled as Ω in order to show, after the optimization, that $\Omega \approx 1$. The results are:

$$\frac{d_c}{R} = \frac{1}{\phi\Omega} \left[\frac{(1 - \nu_{x\theta}\nu_{\theta x})G_{xz}\sigma_o}{2E_xE_\theta} \right]^{1/2} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{t_f}{R} = \left[\frac{3G_{xz}}{2E_oE_xE_\theta} \right]^{1/2} \frac{(1 - \nu_{x\theta}\nu_{\theta x})\sigma_o}{\pi\phi\Omega} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{h_c}{R} = \left[\frac{1 - \nu_{x\theta}\nu_{\theta x}}{E_xE_\theta} \right]^{1/2} \frac{\sigma_o}{\phi\Omega} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{t_c}{R} = \left[\frac{3}{E_oE_xE_\theta} \right]^{1/2} \frac{(1 - \nu_{x\theta}\nu_{\theta x})\sigma_o^{3/2}}{\pi\phi\Omega} \quad (16)$$

Associated with the optimization is a unique applied load index-optimum face stress relationship:

$$\frac{N_x}{R} = \left[\frac{6}{E_oE_xE_\theta} \right]^{1/2} \frac{(1 - \nu_{x\theta}\nu_{\theta x})\sigma_o^2}{\pi\phi\Omega} \left[G_{xz}^{1/2} + \frac{\sigma_o}{G_{xz}^{1/2}} \right] \quad (17)$$

This relationship not only defines σ_o as a function of the applied load index (N_x/R), but expresses the upper limit of the load index since σ_o can never exceed the allowable maximum face stress. To attempt to apply a significantly larger load to a non-optimum construction results in a prohibitive weight penalty.

Finally, the weight relationship can be written as follows for the optimum construction:

$$\frac{W}{R} = \frac{\rho}{\sigma_o} \left(\frac{N_x}{R} \right) \quad (18)$$

However, if one simplifies (17) by making use of the fact that the second term in the bracket is small compared to the first, then an approximate weight equation can be written in terms of the applied load index:

$$\frac{W}{R} = 6^{1/4} \frac{\rho(1 - \nu_{x\theta}\nu_{\theta x})^{1/2} G_{x\theta}^{1/4}}{(E_oE_xE_\theta)^{1/4}} \left(\frac{N_x}{R} \right)^{1/2} \quad (19)$$

For any applied load, it is seen that the obvious factor of merit for the material is

$$F.M. = \frac{1}{\rho} \left[\frac{E_o E_x E_\theta}{G_{xz}} \right]^{1/4} \quad (20)$$

Of course $(1 - \nu_{x\theta}\nu_{\theta x})^{1/2}$ could be included in the denominator, but it has little effect. The material with the highest F.M. results in the shell of least weight for a given applied load. Notice that for an isotropic material, $F.M. = E^{1/2} / \rho$.

5. COMPARISON OF VARIOUS MATERIALS

Using the material properties listed in Table II of Reference 2, the factor of merit F.M. are given below in Table 1. Also given are the values of ϕ and (N_x/R) max.

Table 1. Factors of Merit and Maximum Load Indices for Various Material Systems.

Material	ϕ	F.M.	(N_x/R) max
Boron/6061 Al.	0.766	74.36	3.267
T300 Gr./934 Epoxy	0.5657	66.22	8.067
Boron/Epoxy	0.4806	65.80	
Hi Str. Gr./Epoxy	0.5159	60.34	
7075-T6 Aluminum	1	40.67	1.598

The F.M.'s listed are in units of $10^3 \text{ m}^2/\text{kg} \cdot 1/2$, and the (N_x/R) values are in $10^5 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$. It is seen that the boron-aluminum metal matrix composite has the highest factor of merit of all the materials examined. In fact, using boron-aluminum rather than boron-epoxy results in a structure 12% lighter, while using boron-aluminum saves 45% in weight compared to using 6061-T6 aluminum.

Of course, the ratios of Table 1 only address the materials over the applicable range of applied loads delineated by (17). The upper limits of load index, N_x/R , of some of the materials are shown in Table 1 to show, for example, that even though the boron-aluminum construction realizes a lower weight compared to the T300/934 graphite epoxy, yet the graphite-epoxy construction can withstand loads 146% greater than the boron-aluminum construction. It is also seen that the use of aluminum results in a heavy construction that has major load limitations as well -- quantitatively showing the advantages of using composite materials for this purpose. These upper values of N_x/R are determined by Equation 17, wherein σ_o is the maximum allowable stress for the material.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Analytical methods to use in the analysis, design, and optimization of web core sandwich circular cylindrical shells subjected to an axially-symmetric compressive load are presented and discussed.

It is seen that when a specially orthotropic composite material the 1-direction (primary fiber direction) should always be in the axial direction for this loading.

The equations through (12) and (18) can be used directly in the analysis and design of these structures. The use of (13) through (20) results in the shell of absolute minimum weight, as well as the maximum load index (N_x/R) the optimum or non-optimum shell can resist.

References

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